

Time recognition from JASIST full text – Using BERT and SciBERT

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Introduction

Named entity recognition is the most basic and key task in natural language processing. At present, most named entity recognition starts from two paths: one is based on pattern matching; the other is based on machine learning or deep learning. The method based on pattern matching is the earliest method used by intelligence analysts. In recent years, the method based on machine learning and deep learning has become the mainstream method of named entity recognition. Ali et al. (2019) used deep learning methods to extract algorithm models from academic papers, and then built algorithm road maps to describe the evolutionary relationship between different algorithms. Yao et al. (2020) used CNN+BiLSTM+CRF framework to extract model algorithm entities, and used them as markers to track research characteristics and development process in this field. Extracting knowledge entities from academic papers can provide new research ideas for knowledge discovery, knowledge flow and other issues, and promote the in-depth development of academic evaluation research to a certain extent. However, the research on the identification of time entity in full-text academic texts is not enough. Therefore, BERT and SciBERT models will be applied in this study to identify time entity in full-text academic texts.

Data and Method

Data

In this study, data were from 241 published articles in Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (JASIST).

Entity position distribution

This paper further studies and analyzes the distribution of time entities in different positions of the article, and calculates the position distribution of manually marked time entities in the article. The distribution is calculated according to the percentage of the entity's position in the article. As shown in the Figure 1. below.

Figure 1. Entity position distribution

Method

The BIES method was used to label the time entity, while the other non-time entity are labeled by O. In this paper, the pre-training language model BERT and SciBERT are used as comparison experiment. BERT is a language representation model proposed by Google in 2018. This type of model is a type of neural network model based on a bidirectional Transformer. SCIBERT is a pre-trained language model trained on a scientific corpus, which is more suitable for natural language processing tasks in the direction of scientific papers.

Result

A large number of pre-experiments were performed in the training of the BERT model. The final pre-training model with 12 layers, 768 hidden units, and 12 self-attention heads is applied in this paper. The values of the hyperparameters are as listed below: maximum sequence length 128, batch size 8, learning rate 0.00005, number of epochs 3.0, case insensitive.

Then the 10-fold cross-validation tests were performed with BERT and SciBERT models respectively. The performance of each model was evaluated by P, R and F values, and results are as shown in Table 1 in summary.

Table 1. Results of ten-fold cross validation

NUM.	BERT	SciBERT
1	56.11%	58.09%
2	50.38%	52.33%
3	47.90%	51.34%
4	53.11%	53.82%
5	67.54%	66.33%
6	55.71%	61.15%
7	67.58%	65.95%
8	44.36%	48.44%
9	55.19%	57.51%
10	70.23%	74.15%
AVG_ F	56.81%	58.91%
MAX_ F	70.23%	74.15%

According to the above data, we plotted the maximum F-value and the average F-value of the ten trials as histograms displayed in Figures 2.

Figure 2. Histogram of average F-value and maximum F-value of two models (BERT and SciBERT) in 10-fold cross-validation tests

It can be seen that the results of SciBERT are higher than those of BERT, regardless of the maximum F-value or the average F-value. Overall, the average F values of both BERT and SciBERT are not higher than 80%, both did not work as expected.

Conclusions

This study employed the BERT model and SciBERT model to extract time entity from the academic full text of JASIST. The average F-values of both not higher than 80%, can not achieve the desired effect. Therefore, there is still room for improvement in this paper, although the results are helpful to the exploration and mining of various time entity to some extent. In the future, standardizing entity annotation and choosing other models (e.g., LSTM, BiLSTM) for time entity in academic texts are feasible solutions.

References

- Yao R, Ye Y, Zhang J, et al. AI Marker-based Large-scale AI Literature Mining[J]. arXiv preprint arXiv:2011.00518, 2020.
- Zha H, Chen W, Li K, et al. Mining algorithm roadmap in scientific publications[C]//Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining. 2019: 1083-1092.